

PeCATHS

PHOTO-ELECTROCATALYTIC ROUTES FOR LONG-TERM SUSTAINABLE HYDROGEN STORAGE

What is PECATHS?

PeCATHS is committed to develop an integrated long-term energy storage system utilizing hydrogen in the form of liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), coupled with innovative biomass conversion. This approach enables the direct transfer of hydrogen from biomass to LOHCs without the need of hydrogen gas production, while simultaneously generating high-value chemicals. By integrating chemical and energy sectors, the project aims to synthesize platform chemicals and achieve long-term energy storage in liquid form, enhancing both the sustainability and efficiency of energy systems.

Advantages

A major advantage of LOHC technology is its ability to transform hydrogen gas into a stable liquid energy carrier, significantly facilitating the storage, transport and distribution. To tackle the economic challenges associated with this technology, PeCATHS employs a cost-effective strategy that utilizes biomass as a hydrogen source and solar power as a renewable energy source. This method allows for the direct integration of hydrogen into LOHCs without the complexities of gas compression and storage, thereby reducing costs and enhancing competitiveness against conventional energy storage systems.

<https://pecaths.eu/>

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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
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State Secretariat for Education,
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Benefits

PeCATHS addresses the critical need for sustainable and viable energy storage, transport, and distribution solutions through the use of advanced (photo)electrocatalytic transformations. This project not only aims to reduce operational costs but also seeks to contribute to the development of sustainable energy infrastructures vital for future energy networks.

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